

Modalities for taming the tongue against hate speech for national cohesion and development in Nigeria.

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Abstract

The tongue is a small organ in the human vocal “anatomy used in generating speech sounds. It is the most mobile speech organ, and by its “invisible” configuration, the tongue is like a double-edge sword. It can produce sweet and soured words, encouraging and discouraging words and is capable of “setting up” a beautiful edifice and setting same ablaze. There has been a hue and cry over the use of hate speech by politicians in Nigeria. Hate speech includes words, gestures, writing, and any other linguistic behavior that can spark off negative and inimical responses on the listeners. Such speech floods every media space, especially during electioneering campaigns and in political discourse. The use of hate speech by political gladiators in Nigeria is worrisome and calls for attention. Hate speech are used by the political class to denigrate their opponents, thereby generating crises. This paper examines the use of hate speech and canvases that politicians should eschew hate speech to engender peace and development in Nigeria. Data that instantiates hate speech was culled from social media, print and other electronic media. The data were descriptively and qualitatively analysed using H.P Grice’s cooperative principle theoretical framework.

KEYWORD: Hate Speech, tongue, political gladiators, cooperative principle, crisis, cohesion, development.

Introduction

From creation, language has been a useful tool. Christian religion teaches that the world itself, with its fullness, was framed with language by God. God blessed the first man with language but cursed him when he rebelled. Thus language is like a two edged-sword. The positive use of the tongue leads to peaceful co-existence among individuals which can in turn stimulate cohesion, integration and national unity and development on the contrary, the wrong use of the tongue can trigger a face threatening utterance in an audience and can spark off

disharmony and crisis. The use of "derogative or discriminatory speech has resulted in attempts to exploit fragilities and polarizations with specific nation targeting ordinary users as active participants in the spread of hate and disinformation "(Udukpa, Gagliardone, Deen and (Csuka, 2020 p.2). The laws made against hate speech are only targeted at the down trodden and political opponents, Members of the ruling party in Nigeria seen to be "immune" to these laws.

The alarming use and spread of hate speech by politicians in Nigeria poses a serious threat to national cohesion and capable of tearing Nigeria apart. The most devastating

hate speech flooded the polity, particularly during the general elections of 2015, 2019 and 2023. During these periods, religious and tribal bigots, senior citizens, political stalwarts used hate speech during campaigns. For instance prior to the 2015 general election, Isola (2018 p.5) noted that "traditional and social media contenders deployed derogatory words and terms in local dialects to label and demean opponents".

Igbeaku, Mbah, Ikan, Ude, Achandu, Odo and Igbeaku (2024. P2) and Olowojolu (2016) observed that "members of the ruling party, particularly All Progressive Alliance (APC) have used their privately owned media outlets, the Nigerian Television Authority (NTA) and Federal Radio Corporation of Nigeria (FRCN) owned by the federal government to proliferate hate speech during elections".

This present beams light on the incidences of hate speech by the political class in Nigeria to ascertain its linguistic Implications in national cohesion, peace and development. The main thrust is to address this ugly practice during election campaigns and discourse, to bring do light the implicatures of floating Maxim of conversational cooperation principles in national cohesion. The paper is of the view that if politicians can be trained to tame their tongues, they will eschew hate speech and base their campaigns on issues and ideologies. Thus, it advocate for a paradigm shift from the present manner politicians deployed speech during elections.

Statement of Problem

The proliferation of hate speech among politicians in Nigeria is becoming a threat to the unity of our nation. No matter how we strive as a people to build infrastructure and stimulate our economy towards growth and development, our efforts will be a fiasco, if we are not united. Hate speech is one of the cankerworms eating deep into the very fabric of the Nigerian State. Unfortunately, the different governments have not addressed this "monster" adequately. Thus, disunity is thriving favourably. Language is one of the best tools given to man to conduct his daily affairs. A courteous speech promotes peaceful co-existence, harmony, love and cohesion amongst people. On the contrary, a face - threatening speech is inimical to national unity. The biblical "Tower of Babel" collapsed not because the engineers were not skillful, but because of disunity caused by linguistic heterogeneity. The development we seek as a people, will continue to elude us since there is division among us. This social disharmony as shown in the study is largely caused by hate speech among the political class and their followers. To change the present trend, our leaders need to tame their tongues. This is the main thrust of this paper.

Literature Review

Hate speech

Hate speech refers to offensive discourse targeting a group or an individual based on

inherent characteristics such as race, religion, political affiliation and can threaten social peace. It is abusive or face threatening speech or writing that expresses prejudice on the basis of ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation or similar background. "Hate speech not only causes harm at the personal level and can incite violence, it is an attack on inclusion diversity and human right (UNESCO 2024) Cohen-Almagor (2013, p. 43) defines hate speech as " a bias motivated, hostile, malicious speech aimed at a person or a group of people because of some of their actual or perceived innate characteristics". Hate speech coupled with disinformation can lead to stigmatization, discrimination, and large-scale violence. The origin of hate speech in Nigeria is traceable to the pre-independence era, though the colonial lords managed its negative manifestations. Seng and Hunt (1986) cited in Igbeaku et al (2024) report that "the first inciting hate speech were made by the then Sardauna of Sokoto, Sir Ahmadu Bello, the presidential candidate of Nigeria People's Party (NPP) in both 1979 and 1983 general elections, Dr Nnamdi Azikiwe and the national chairman of Unity Party of Nigeria (UPN) Chief Obafemi Awolowo". According to Igbeaku et al, this fact fueled the polity for electoral violence, sectarian killings, and military coups.

Thus, the founding fathers of Nigeria ate soured grapes, and the teeth of present-day politicians are set on edge.

UN (2013) states that hate speech includes:

- i. All dissemination of ideas based on racial or ethnic superiority or hatred by whichever means

- ii. Incitement to hatred, contempt or discrimination against members of a group on grounds of their race, colour, descent or national or ethnic origin
- iii. Threats or incitement to violence against persons or groups on the grounds in (ii) above
- iv. Expressions of insults, ridicule or slander of persons or groups or justification or hatred, contempt or discrimination on the grounds in (ii) above, when it clearly amounts to incitement to hatred, discrimination and (iv) participation in organizations or activities, which promote and incite racial discrimination.

Politicians use religious groups and ethnic affiliation as spokesperson when expressing hate speech. They use this to buy the sympathy of the members of their religious groups and ethnicity. Eloquent examples include the agitation for Sovereign Biafra Republic, Niger Delta Republic, Arewa Republic and Oduduwa republic and other ethnic groups during the 2019 and 2023 general elections. These agitations were so inflammable that the cooperate existence of Nigeria almost went into coma. The outcome of these agitations was the formation of several militant groups in South South, IPOB in South East, Boko Haram/Bandits in the North, and Amotekun in South West. Today, these different groups are a thorn in the flesh of the nation.

People who use hate speech have selfish reasons. Gorka (2019) notes the following as reasons why people use hate speech;

- i. The opportunity to relieve tension and getting rid of frustration
- ii. The desire to hurt and humiliate people
- iii. It is a way of fighting to be respected in their environment.
- iv. They try to make their images better by hurting other people and making them weaker
- v. Hate speech is a way of gaining power over another group of people, a form of justifying their worse positions (on ethnic, religious or political grounds)
- vi. Lack of control throughout actions and the feeling of helplessness.

Ilori (2023) cited in Igbeaku et al (2024: 4) posits that "the specific ways to minimize hate speech in Nigeria while securing the right to freedom of speech is by making Nigerians to be abided by the International human rights law on hate speech. The International human rights law is a body of rules to which Sovereign states subscribe.

The transition to civil rule decree 1999 cited in Ugwu (2010) states that "abusive, interpret, slanderous or base language designed or likely to provoke violence emotions or reactions should not be employed or used in political campaigns" in spite of various laws prohibiting hate speech and libel, politicians in Nigeria still generously use hate speech.

NATIONAL COHESION

For a nation to be peaceful and develop, all its strata need to be knitted harmoniously. Igbeaku et al (2024:4) defines national cohesion as "the act of bringing together a

variety of individuals from different cultural, ethnic and social backgrounds in a specific setting or polity for a peaceful co-existence and growth of the nation". The maturity of a people is x-rayed in their ability to harness their beauty in their diverse nature epitomized in their culture, religion, political affiliations, and linguistic structure for their benefit. This underscores the aphorism "there is unity in diversity".

National integration is possible only if people from different ethnic, cultural, political, and ideological backgrounds within a nation have a complete allegiance to their nation over and above their ethnic and individual, (Usman 2015: 30) defines national cohesion as:

A process that produces an omnibus of initiatives put in place by a state, its representative or institution guided by respect for the unique traditions and cultural background of ethnicities sharing the same polity with the goal of harmonizing all interest, through a form of dialogue and representation and addressing differences in sharing of resources, benefits, opportunities and responsibilities in order to guarantee stability, longevity

and prosperity of the polity as long as the inhabitants decide to remain in the polity.

To attain the position captured by Umaru and Usman is quite cumbersome. This is because when a "mixed multitude" conglomerates, social friction, political dissension, economic rivalries and historical contrarities are inevitable. The only solution to such problem is for the people to avert ethnic jingoism, religious bigotry and cultural prejudice.

From all available literature, efforts have been made by different nations to minimize hate speech during elections. For instance, in Nigeria, there are laws against libel and defamation of characters. Unfortunately, the judiciary is like the fingers of a leprous hand. This paper suggest modalities to eschew hate speech.

Theoretical framework”.

The work tilts towards H.P (Grice 1975) Cooperative principles (CP). Grice notes that as social beings, when people talk, they do so with other humans. Thus each interlocutor ought to speak sincerely, relevantly, lucidly as well as provide sufficient information in a speech event. Grice CP entails four quadriple Maxim's of quality, quantity, relevance and manner. The first three maxim: quantity, quality and relevance relate to the ingredient of the message, the last one which is "manner" is concerned with how the message is conveyed. The Maxim of quantity requires that the speaker should provide as much information as necessary (Ndimele (2007: 143) notes that “the speaker should not make his contribution to the subject

matter of the conversation more or less informative than is necessary”. If the speaker makes his contribution more or less informative than is needed, the Maxim of quantity is violated. The maxim of quality demands that participants in a speech event must say what is true and not what they know is false. The speaker should not say what he has no evidence to support. The maxim of relevance or relation requires that what the speaker says is suitable to the context of communication. Grice (1975) avers that under Maxim of manner, participants must avoid "unnecessary prolixity". This maxim informs conversationalist to be lucid.

This paper uses CP as a tool to discover the workability of these conversational maxims in the hate speech of politicians during elections. During conversation, at times, interlocutors flout these maxims. This occurs when communicators break the maxims furtively such that other people do not know.

Data Analysis

Maxim of quantity

This maxim is used to access a speech to ascertain if the message conveyed is informative as expected and not more or less informative. Examples are:

1. "And what is wrong with South East transmitting into a full blown independent BIAFRAN country away from the fraud, contraption, and deceptive "Democratic" Nigeria, where criminals are called princes, Emirs, Chiefs, Kings, Obis, Ezes Where

there is an official reward for "criminals".

2. "Only people who can accept the pain of rigging should participate in an election.
3. "They are killing my people in public, after killing my people, they want to try me in private? That person is mad. I won't allow it, tell Bihari that's what I said, that he is mad. He cannot jail me, he is a mad man.
4. "If they contest (Northerners) they are wasting their time, he who pays the Piper will dictate the tune. We own them. We are feeding them. They are parasites. A beggar has no choice.... They are beggars and parasites.

The above extracts are indices of the Maxim of quantity violation. The flouting of cooperative principle engendered the creation of conventional implicatures. They contain information that are not necessary. The implicature of violating the Maxim here gives credence to the inference that generate more meaning or additional meaning to the utterance. Thus the utterances acquire a better meaning at a deeper plane or interpretation. The repetition of " he is mad, he cannot jail, he is a mad man and "we own them, we are feeding them... They are parasites etc, where criminals are are called princes, emirs, Chiefs, Obis, Ezes are not necessary, although they have interferences retrievable only at the deeper level. This inferences are calculated establishment of conventional and conversational implicatures capable of eroding national cohesion, religious tolerance, political Harmony and ethnic integration.

Maxims of manner

The Maxim of manner requires the speaker to avoid obscurity, ambiguity, unnecessary prolixity and to make the utterances orderly. The utterances in the following excerpts fall short of this maxim.

5. Northerners need to vote for me rather than a Yoruba or Igbo candidate because I am a pan-Nigerian of a northern extraction that has built bridges across the country.
6. "Yorubas must deliver 95% of their votes to me, reject Atiku, Obi. You don't need them"
7. "This time, it's Yoruba turn and in Yoruba land, it's my tenure, "Emilokan"
8. "I'm a BIAFRAN and we are going to crumble the zoo. Some idiots who are not educated said that they will arrest me and I ask them to come. I am in Biafra land. If any of them leaves Biafra land alive know that this is not IPOB. Tell them that".

The above extracts are not presented in an orderly manner and also convey additional interpretations. As such they violate the Maxim of manner. For instance, Atiku in (5) telling the Northerners to vote for him because he is a Northerner. This same can be Said of Tinubu in extracts 6 and 7. Both candidates based their campaigns on ethno-

religious sentiments instead of what they intend to achieve when voted for. Extract 8 also flouts the Maxim of manner. Being educated does not immune someone against the law. Education enables one to think and reason logically. It enables one eschew actions outlawed by the society. Regardless the level of education attained by a man, he can be arrested by any appropriate authority, if he contravened the rule of law.

The interference that can be drawn from the utterance is that the speaker has formidable "Powers" that fortify him against any arrest.

Maxim of Quality

This maxim demands that a speaker should not say anything for which he lacks evidence or which he knows-[is not true. This maxim is flouted if a speaker deliberately deviates from the cooperative principle of conversation to create implicatures.

Consider the following excerpts

9. "All he could do was to boast that he saves money..... It is a heartless governor who holds back Money when people went hungry, schools, roads and clinics went in disrepair, neither the city dwellers nor farmers prospered under him. In the end he refused to save the people because he preferred to save money".
- 10."Kashim Shettima is the grand commander of Bandits.
- 11.Obaseki's wife is barren"
- 12.Adams Oshiomole is to APC What Modu Sheriff was to PDP. The only difference is that PDP had enough time

before the election to eject Modu Sheriff while APC has no such luxury..... Today APC now resembles Oshiomole's physical appearance".

13."IPOB is a terrorist group"

14."That someone's head was sliced with matched does not mean that the rerun was not peaceful"

The above utterances violate the Maxim of quality because they are fallacious as the speakers could not advance evidences to substantiate them. The utterance in (9) is vagued and illogical as the speaker could not justify his claims that his opponent saved money in order to impoverish his subjects in Anambra State.

The same is true of 10 and 11. There is no court ruling that proved that "Shetima is a commander of bandits. There is no medical report to prove that Obaseki's wife is barren "Today APC now resembles Oshiomole's physical appearance is illogical and fallacious. The physical appearance of Oshiomole is not tantamount with the fortune of APC his political party because "a hood does not make a munk". He may be physically "inadequate" but very "adequate" upstairs. No wonder his party won the 2019 and 2023 general elections as declared by INEC.

Again, the proscribing of IPOB as a terrorist group by Federal High Court on September 20, 2017 was misleading. IPOB is a group of armless and a non violent people agitating for the succession and freedom of Biafra from Nigeria. More so, the declaration that an election was peaceful with clear evidences of violence proven by the slicing of someone's

head with matchet is contextually unrealistic, insincere, and ridiculous.

From the forgoing, the speakers excellently crafted the speeches to Hoodwink people, thereby violating the Maxim of quality.

Maxim of Relevance

The Maxim of Relevance or relation indicates that an utterance should be relevant or related to the topic or subject of discussion. The Maxim disallows any contribution to a discourse which is extraneous. In the following data the Maxim of relevance is flouted.

15. "Everybody knows the schools I attended. When I was the governor in Anambra, Everybody knows what I did, all the work I did.... Everybody knows where I live, go and verify"
16. "Dele Momodu is huffing and puffing without substance. He and his team are a group of photographers and video editors with tabloid-centred minds".
17. Keyamo is a certified nuisance and political neophyte working as a Bola Tinubu's lapdog".
18. "Dino Melaye is a butt-loving, rectum sucking, skin-bleaching tout".
19. "I don't know which party my wife belongs to, but she belongs to my kitchen and my living room and the other room.
20. "It is going to be rig and roast. We are prepared not to go to court but to drive them out".

In (11), the expressions "everybody knows the school I attended" and "everybody knows where I live" are not relevant in the context. The speaker might have used it to mock an opponent who has questionable academic records. This information is retrievable only at the deep level of interpretations to 16-18 are mere verbal altercations among political jobbers who are demonstrating their wit and unleashing linguistic "Arsenal" to denigrate opponents. The speakers flout the Maxim of relevance as they do not contribute to political discourse. The last part of (19) is very irrelevant to the subject at hand. It shows how neck deep the speaker is Attached to the Islamic tenet of "purdahism". The Implication of the irrelevant answer in (19) is that the speaker failed to observe the Maxim of relevance and consequently gives the listener the inference that generate additional meaning than the semantic surface level.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

Section 97 of the electoral Act 2022 In Nigeria recommends a sanction to any candidate, person or association that engages in campaign achored on religious, tribal or sectional reason. The offender is liable to conviction to a maximum of #1m or 12 months imprisonment or both. But the law seems incapable of scaring politician from using hate speech. The data analyzed above are just a few of hate speech used by politicians. There is no assurance that there will be a paradigm shift in electioneering campaign in the nearest future. The proposed bill to establish Electoral offences tribunal is

still gathering dust in the National Assembly. It may have been entangled in the web of still-birth bills. Worse still, if passed, members of the ruling party and politicians who are ready to buy judgment will make the law "null and void". Based on this, we make the following recommendations:

First, we need to go back to the basics when oratory and rhetorics were accorded relevance in the school curriculum. The study of rhetorics rested on a special kind of attitude to language as a means through which the listener could be influenced in the manner desired by the speaker or writer. Ataman(2010) notes that "rhetorical skills according to plato "should not be put to unscrupulous use but to make truth plainer, arouse desirable emotions and to help good purpose". Akpojisheri (2016:131) posits that "Plato in his teaching insists that the orator, having discovered the truth, must present it in a manner acceptable to his audience".

Ekpe(1992) cited in Akpojisheri (2016:131) reports that Aristotle distinguished three types of oratory: deliberative, e.g political speech which urges the audience to do or not to do something, forensic which attacks or defends a person, and ceremonial, which praises or censures.

From the revelation of Rein (1969) cited in Ekpe (1992, a speaker or politician should possess the following skills:

- a) His ability to use language to create and maintain interest.
- b) His ability to structure and state his points with clarity and force.

- c) His ability to sound relevant and competent. This is because meaning will not occur if the listener feels the speaker is not speaking to the point.
- d) His ability to use an appropriate logical and emotional appeal, and
- e) His ability to match the subject, the purpose and the occasion of communication.

Rein's position could be adopted by politicians in their campaigns. There would have to be workshops and seminars where politicians are properly exposed to the acts of rhetoric and oratory. This discipline should be re-introduced into the school curriculum from primary to tertiary levels, apart from the Department of philosophy.

Second, media practioners and journalists should stop "advertising" hate speech. The practice of using hate speech by politicians to market media outlets should be discouraged. Media practioners and content makers in the social media would have to "purge" their editorial, articles and write-ups of hate speech.

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